

Coding is not enough

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Abstract

This work reflects on the evolution of the Research Software Engineer community since the term emerged at a Software Sustainability Institute workshop in 2012. With the rise of large language models, routine coding support is likely to decline, reinforcing the need for deeper engagement with research itself. We reiterate the importance of recognising research software as a core scholarly output within frameworks such as the Research Excellence Framework. In this context, we believe that the long-term sustainability of Research Software Engineers is closely linked to their deeper integration within the research lifecycle.

1 Let's have a look back...

In 2012, at a Software Sustainability Institute workshop in Oxford, a community of software-literate research staff from various research domains began to branch out from traditional academic roles. During this meeting, the term Research Software Engineers (RSEs) was created.

These individuals were working in research, often as postdocs or early-career staff, and were primarily writing software to support their research, which was increasingly essential. In the State of the Nation Brett et al. [2017] it is said:

“Researchers solve problems that are highly specific to their field of expertise. These problems cannot be solved by the straightforward application of off-the-shelf software, so researchers develop tools that are tailored to their exact needs.”

Unfortunately the traditional academic career pathways poorly recognised and rewarded software development as a core part of research.

Significant effort has been made to build a community of RSEs. The RSE association was created in 2013 and was replaced by the RSE society in 2019 and now has 700 paying members with a RSE society slack workspace of thousands of members. At University level, progress has been made and RSE teams have been created. Teams have emerged at multiple Universities across the UK and the movement spread into other countries, such as the US, the Netherlands, Germany, and an International Council of RSE Associations has been created with a charter adopted in 2021¹.

Looking at the current landscape, there is no single recipe for building RSE teams. Some teams are embedded in academic departments, some others have been created in University's central services and some are a mix of the two. As a result, two types of RSEs are living next to each other: the embedded RSEs collaborating closely with the researchers, contributing to the full research lifecycle, from grant applications to research output generation; and the support RSEs who is given a well-

¹<https://researchsoftware.org/council/charter.html>

defined tasks by the researcher that they focus on entirely and produce a professional piece of work, as highlighted in the State of the Nation [Brett et al. \[2017\]](#):

“By establishing a service function, the creation of high-quality, impactful code can be the sole goal of the RSEs, who are not distracted by the competing career demands experienced by researchers”.

In other words, support RSEs are here to code, and just code. And to fit into this new “service” environment, they have been placed on professional service contracts. Compared to traditional academic contracts, professional services contracts do not have incentives to actually be part of the research lifecycle, from grant bidding to dissemination. The recent [Research Software Maintenance Fund \[RSMF\]](#) call is interesting. This call, created by the [Software Sustainability Institute](#) and supported by UKRI, is a major programme to fund vital pieces of the research software ecosystem. This was perfect for RSEs. A call made for software in research could reasonably expect to be overflowing with applications from RSEs. However, statistics of the first round show that less than a quarter of the applications were led by RSEs. It is unclear whether this low percentage of RSEs leading grants is due to institutional restrictions or a lack of incentives to apply for grants, even when it is so aligned with their skill set.

2 A change is needed

Historically, RSEs distinguished themselves through their software expertise and the robustness of their tools. Today, however, we face a crucial turning point in software development history. The rise of large language models, now used globally, is dramatically accelerating the creation of software. As coding agents become part of the furniture, writing code is becoming a smaller part of the software engineering role. Consequently, the demand of researchers to need help with their coding might dramatically reduce. Debugging, refactoring code, documentation, boilerplate, basic infrastructure, scripting and translating code between languages are likely to (at least partially) disappear from our work. In

this context, the quote by [Chue Hong et al. \[2025\]](#) is interesting:

“The need for an RSE to develop code on behalf of a researcher is disappearing, but there is still a requirement for a skilled professional to provide the assurance that the software is correct.”

The first part is clear, if a researcher can explain what they need coding, then do they need a RSE? The second part is true as well, but ultimately, the only people who can say that a software is correct, are the researchers themselves, or the RSEs with enough domain knowledge to make that decision. RSEs are in a better position, if they are understanding the research. This was already clear 14 years ago at the beginning of the RSE movement, as shown by [this](#) SSI blog post:

“One can’t create or maintain software without thoroughly understanding the system it describes.”

Academia is changing already. This recent post (see [Fig. 1](#)) in the RSE Slack channel is illustrating this point perfectly and shows that some funder are already considering RSE work as replaceable labor. Continuous justification of the RSE position may be needed. But would a funder ask to cut the research time? The world and academia will not wait for us to justify our existence, these tools are becoming the new standard. We have to demonstrate that RSEs work is much more than writing code.

Other actors in the RSE worlds are changing as well. The Journal of open source software (JOSS), a journal specifically for software and a natural publishing place for RSEs, has recently changed its submission requirements. The [latest version](#) of the JOSS documentation now states:

“Whether or not you use AI assistance in your development, submissions should demonstrate the irreplaceable human contributions: problem framing, key design decisions, thoughtful architectural choices, and practices that make software usable and sustainable for others.”

To get credit for your research software, it is essential to demonstrate work other than code. This is logical as the time cost, of writing code approaches zero, more value is naturally attributed to the design and impact of the software, rather than the

Figure 1: Capture of a slack thread in the RSE community slack (Reproduced with the agreement from the original poster).

code itself. As software engineers, this is jarring as most of us love writing code and take great pride in it. Unfortunately, the rest of the world doesn't necessarily share this view and care more about the software's functionality than how it is written. Is a researcher going to spend the extra time onboarding a new RSE, explaining specific software requirements with all the human hours this takes, for some beautifully written code? Or will they put their software requirements into a coding agent, go to bed, and wake up to something that works but maybe is a little less elegantly implemented?

What lies ahead? Short answer, nobody really knows. It is not easy to estimate the long term impact that the rise of AI will have on the RSE community. It could go many ways:

- The software boom: given the increasing capacity of AI and the increase in data volume, more and more researchers want to use it to analyse data. As a consequence, there is great demand for new AI analysis, data mining, software building which leads to more AI-RSE work.
- The RSE bypass loop and Technical debt: As generative AI makes "coding" very easy, researchers use it to write their code and bypass RSEs. These new tools create lot of software that are not understood well enough to be fixed or maintained in the long term. RSEs are required to clean the technical debt. We are not needed to do creative work anymore, which is what building a software is, but we are called

to be software firefighters, called when things are going sideways.

It is hard to see if one side will be favored. Both could actually be true at the same time. However, it is clear that this new landscape will have consequences on the RSE community. Whether it is change of job profile, a change in demand, with either much more work or much less of it, this is something that the community has to reflect on.

However, if we want to continue to be part of the creative process of research, the future of RSE is not done **by supporting** researchers from the sideline, **but by actively collaborating** within the research community.

3 Research software *is* research

Software is not yet widely seen as a traditional research output. The academic cycle largely revolves around bidding for money, doing research, publishing papers and getting cited. The [Research Excellence Framework](#) asks universities to gather research outputs, and these are overwhelmingly traditional papers. This is the current reality.

However, in the last decade, progress has been made toward recognising research software through more traditional publication channels. More journals are now accepting software papers as submissions. Some are domain specific, such as Astronomy and Computing, Advances in Engineering Software, Transactions on Mathematical Software,

Journal of Software for Algebra and Geometry, and Artificial Life. Others are more generalist, such as Software Impacts, Journal of Open Research Software, and Journal of Open Source Software. These venues give RSEs a place to participate in the academic process, and they should be used much more widely than they currently are.

In addition, both national and international initiatives were launched in the recent years and support the recognition of software. The San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment ([DORA](#)) aims at recognising that:

“The outputs from scientific research are many and varied, including: research articles reporting new knowledge, data, reagents, and software; intellectual property; and highly trained young scientists.”

DORA has been signed by 3600 organisations worldwide (almost 300 in the UK, including UKRI). In the UK, the recent [Hidden REF](#) movement has been created to recognise everyone involved in the research process, acknowledging that research is fundamentally collaborative. As the initiative’s website states:

“If we don’t recognise everyone involved in research, we limit our ability to conduct research.”

This applies plainly to RSEs: If you write research software, software that directly collects data, processes data, or generates research results, you should be credited in the research findings and the software you write should be published or at the very least be given a mean to be cited. This idea is not new and was already around 30 years ago, as paraphrased in [Buckheit and Donoho \[1998\]](#):

“An article about computational science in a scientific publication is not the scholarship itself, it is merely advertising of the scholarship. The actual scholarship is the complete software development environment and the complete set of instructions which generated the figures.”

To put it another way, research software is very often the actual research. Software is now so deeply embedded in the vast majority of research projects from data collection, to data processing, to the generation of results and research dissemination that boundaries between software and research are increasingly disappearing. In this context, the paper

by [Chue Hong et al. \[2025\]](#), titled “The future of research software is the future of research” could perhaps be read differently as: “The future of research is the future of research software.”

If we create tools that collect data, process them, develop the software that produces research results, and publish these software, then **RSEs are researchers**. However, this only works if RSEs are genuinely part of the research process and not only involved to write code. Tasks that might previously have taken three weeks can now sometimes be completed in two days using a large language model. If RSEs are brought into projects for only a few weeks, this RSE model becomes difficult to sustain.

For these reasons, software-literate people in academia must have their work recognised, evaluated and rewarded as traditional research output. This has been proposed in other places (e.g. [Gomez-Diaz and Recio \[2019\]](#), [Canteaut et al. \[2021\]](#)) and this should be the primary goal of this community.

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